

Popular Article

Climate Change Impact on Livestock

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Abstract

Livestock has a two-way impact on climate change in general. firstly, the livestock's contribution to climate change, and second is how climate change affects livestock. As a result, boosting livestock productivity in a changing climate scenario requires reducing both livestock greenhouse gas emissions and the impact of climate change on livestock output. Under the changing climate scenario, these activities will optimize cattle output. By 2050, global demand for animal products is predicted to quadruple, owing primarily to rising global living standards. Meanwhile, the influence of climate change on feed crop and forage quality, water availability, animal and milk production, livestock illnesses, animal reproduction, and biodiversity poses a threat to livestock production.

Introduction (Junaidi et al; 2020)

By 2050, the world's population is predicted to grow from 7.2 billion to 9.6 billion people (UN, 2013). This is a 33% increase in population, but as the global quality of living rises, demand for agricultural products will rise by almost 70% in the same time span (FAO, 2009). In the meantime, total global cultivated land area has remained constant since 1991, indicating greater productivity and intensification initiatives. Climate change, competition for land and water, and food security at a time when it is most required are all expected to have a negative impact on livestock output.

Consequences of climate change

Climate change has direct consequences for livestock in terms of growth, milk production, reproduction, metabolic activity, and illness occurrence. Climate change has indirect effects on livestock through diminishing the availability of water, pasture, and other feed resources. Mitigating the effects of environmental stress on cattle necessitates multidisciplinary approaches that prioritize animal nutrition, housing, and health. It is critical to comprehend and assess livestock responses to the environment in order to make nutritional and environmental management changes that will improve animal comfort and performance. Alcohol use have also been reported.

Most key aspects of livestock production, such as water availability, animal production, reproduction, and health, are affected by temperature. Temperature, CO₂ levels, and precipitation variations all have an impact on forage quantity and quality. Temperature and precipitation variations have a major impact on livestock illnesses.

A thermal comfort zone exists in all animals, which is a range of ambient environmental temperatures that are helpful to physiological activities. Temperature, humidity, species, genetic potential, life stage, and nutritional state all influence heat stress in livestock. Because livestock in lower latitudes are normally better acclimated to high temperatures and droughts, livestock in higher latitudes will be more affected by rising temperatures than livestock in lower latitudes. Heat stress reduces forage intake, milk output, feed conversion efficiency, and performance.

Heat stress can decrease the reproductive efficiency of both sexes of livestock. It has an effect on oocyte growth and quality, embryo development, and pregnancy rate in cows and pigs. Increased energy shortfalls and heat stress may jeopardize cow reproduction. In bulls, pigs, and poultry, stress has been linked to reduced sperm concentration and quality.

Climate change's impact on cattle diseases is determined by geographical location, land use type, disease characteristics, and animal susceptibility. Climate change, particularly rising temperatures, can have a direct or indirect impact on animal health. The direct impacts are linked to rising temperatures, which raise the risk of sickness and death. Climate change's indirect consequences include changes in microbial populations (pathogens or parasites), the spread of vector-borne diseases, food-borne diseases, host resistance, and feed and water availability.

Conclusion

To protect cattle production, climate change adaptation, mitigation measures, and policy frameworks are essential. Diversification of livestock animals, the use of multiple crop varieties, and the transition to mixed crop-livestock systems appear to be the most promising adaptation measures among the studies examined. If we wish to address climate change and livestock production with effective adaptation and mitigation methods, we need to scale them up through legislation.

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